

THE ROLE OF MATHEMATICS IN HUMAN LIFE AND DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO TEACHING IT

Sunnatullo Do'stov¹, Xushboqova Saodat Qo'chqor qizi²
Aliyeva Munavvar Tojimirzayevna³

¹ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti
Boshlang'ich ta'lim metodikasi kafedrası o'qituvchisi

^{2,3} O'zbekiston Respublikasi Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti
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ABSTRACT

In this article, the role of mathematics in human life and different approaches to its teaching, the goals and tasks of mathematics education, the priority directions for the development of mathematics education, the development of educational and methodological support of mathematics are discussed.

Introduction:

Mathematics is the basis of knowledge of the universe, and it is important in revealing the specific laws of the surrounding events and phenomena, as well as in the development of production, science and technology, and technologies.

Competency approach to mathematical education implies acquisition by students of various forms of skills that allow them to act effectively in situations encountered in professional, personal and everyday life in society. Thus, in the competency-based approach, the foundation of mathematical education is focused on strengthening the practical, applied directions.

In order to strengthen students' interest in learning general education subjects through the formation of basic competencies and the completion of small educational research, practical exercises and implementation and project work were included in science curricula. This situation not only improves the quality of mastering of a specific academic subject, but also opens opportunities for inter-discipline and connection of science with everyday life and increases the effectiveness of education.

Literature analysis and methodology:

In the organization of mathematics classes, it is necessary to pay more attention to practice than to theory and to some extent abandon the approach based on providing students with ready-made educational materials. It is recommended to use more interactive methods such as cases, research, projects, small learning discoveries in mathematics classes.

It is necessary to use scientific research methods such as observation, experiment, measurements, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, comparison and analogy in the formation of minor research skills in students. It is important not only to form knowledge and skills in students, but also to acquire competencies to apply them in life situations.

In the general secondary education system, it is determined that basic competencies are formed in students along with subject-related competencies. It is appropriate to focus on the formation of basic competences in students through the subjects of the block of specific subjects and their ability to apply the skills and qualifications they have acquired in various situations.

The approach to the creation of national educational standards in mathematics is systematic, that is, put into a specific system, and it is called "Al-jabr". This name has a special meaning of "recovery". The standards cover all students as widely as possible from the beginning of education, and ensure the opportunity for their full participation in the learning process and the maximum participation of students with special needs in the field of education. The standards set clear milestones that all students must meet to prepare for further education and employment. More precisely, standards should define what students understand and can do.

The importance of mathematics education is determined by its role in the development of science and technology, in the production areas of information and communication technologies, and in everyday life. In addition to training creative and creative personnel to meet economic requirements, quality education should also be provided to those who use these achievements as consumers.

Results:

The rapid development of science and technology, the globalization of the world, and the development of information and communication technologies change people's outlook, ways of achieving success, human potential, ability, and creativity serve as the main capital of society.

In this case, the formation of each student's personality in the society to be competitive in the society, to form a perfect person who is flexible to the changing socio-economic environment, active, socially mature potential, possessor of high level of knowledge, mentally and spiritually trained is one of the tasks before our state.

The main tasks of teaching mathematics:

- ensuring that students acquire knowledge and skills about mathematical concepts, properties, forms, methods and algorithms; understanding the importance of mathematics in human development and social development, socio-economic relations, successful application of mathematical knowledge and skills in everyday life teaching to learn;
- formation of independent learning skills while developing individual characteristics of students;
- formation of national and universal human values, creativity in students, taking into account the integration of disciplines, and directing them to consciously choose a profession;
- to a certain extent abandoning the approach based on theoretical teaching of mathematics and providing students with ready-made educational materials, to achieve the formation and development of the student's ability to apply mathematical knowledge in everyday life, independent thinking of students demonstrate and activate skills.

Bringing mathematics education to a new qualitative level at school depends directly on the potential, professional skills and creativity of school teachers. Therefore, improving the qualifications of mathematics teachers, equipping them with modern educational methods and technologies is one of the most pressing issues facing mathematics education.

The integration of our country into the world community, the development of science, technology and technology, the competitiveness of the young generation in the changing world requires the perfect mastery of sciences, which means the introduction of international experiences and models into the education system, including the teaching of mathematics.

Competency approach to mathematical education implies acquisition by students of various forms of skills that allow them to act effectively in situations encountered in professional, personal and everyday life in society. Thus, in the competency-based approach, the foundation of mathematical education is focused on strengthening the practical, applied directions.

Discussion:

Practical exercises and implementation and project work were included in science curricula in order to strengthen students' interest in learning general education subjects by forming basic competencies and performing small educational research. This situation not only improves the quality of mastering of a specific academic subject, but also opens opportunities for inter-discipline and connection of science with everyday life and increases the effectiveness of education.

In the organization of mathematics lessons, it is necessary to pay more attention to practice than theory and to some extent abandon the approach based on providing students with ready-made educational materials.

It is recommended to use more interactive methods such as cases, research, projects, small learning discoveries in mathematics classes. It is necessary to use scientific research methods such as observation, experiment, measurements, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, comparison and analogy in the formation of minor research skills in students.

Arousing interest in mathematics depends on the high level of the teaching method and how skillfully the educational work is built. Each student should be active in class, work with pleasure and use the emergence and development of a passion for knowledge as a starting point, focus on deepening their interest in knowledge.

This is especially important in determining the constant interest and interest of teenagers in this or that subject, when it is reshaped. At this point, the math needs to be applied quickly.

In the process of teaching mathematics, mathematical proverbs also serve as a factor in educating children in the spirit of humanity and hard work.

In order to teach mathematics to young people, it is necessary for a teacher to know these subjects well, to be able to skillfully use teaching methods. At the same time, it is necessary to have deep knowledge of pedagogy, psychology and other sciences. The main purpose of the training is to develop students' intellectual abilities, independent choice and decision-making skills, and to acquire the necessary knowledge.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that every mathematical conclusion studied in mathematics classes requires rigor, which in turn is represented by many mathematical concepts and laws. During the students' gradual study of these laws, their logical thinking develops, and the culture of making mathematical conclusions is formed.

Arousing interest in mathematics depends on the quality of the teaching methodology and the level of educational activity. Each student should work actively and with pleasure in the

lesson, use the emergence and development of enthusiasm for knowledge as a starting point, and focus on deepening interest in learning.

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